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Improved wind speed estimation and rain quantification with continuous-wave wind lidar

Liqin Jin, Nikolas Angelou, Jakob Mann, Gunner Chr. Larsen

Department of Wind Energy, Technical University of Denmark, Frederiksborgvej 399, 4000 Roskilde, Denmark

E-mail: liqn@dtu.dk

Abstract. The presence of raindrops has an adverse impact on the line-of-sight wind speed measurement of Doppler lidars. Here, we propose a method to improve the accuracy of wind speed estimation through a filtering process on rapidly sampled (3000 Hz) lidar data. For this purpose, we conducted a field study at the Risø campus of the Technical University of Denmark using a ground-based, continuous-wave Doppler lidar. Data was acquired during a three-hour period with rain. We propose that we can differentiate between the rain and aerosol back-scattering signals by assessing the maximum of the noise-normalized Doppler spectra. To reduce the influence of rain on the velocity signal, we filter away the Doppler spectra where the maximum is larger than a given threshold. The comparison between the raw and the filtered lidar data with sonic anemometer measurements acquired at the same location, shows that we can effectively remove rain signals and improve the measurement accuracy of a Doppler lidar. However, this method is not applicable when the back-scattering of aerosols and rain are characterized by the same statistics.

1. Introduction

Doppler lidars have been established as valuable tools for wind energy. They can be used for wind resource estimation both onshore [1] and offshore [2], mainly with profiling lidars and scanning lidars [3, 4]. In addition to the mean wind, lidars are also used to estimate turbulence, albeit with greater difficulty [5, 6], to achieve an improved wind turbine control by nacelle mounted lidars to increase the power production [7, 8], and to reduce load through lidar prevision of the incoming gusts [9, 10]. Therefore, the precise determination of the wind speed is paramount for many wind energy applications.

However, in practice, heavy rain can influence the measured line-of-sight velocity of continuous-wave (cw) Doppler lidars, because raindrops may have a different projected speed relative to the lidar beam direction, in comparison to the real wind speed, especially when the beam is not pointing horizontally. It is therefore important to be able to separate the wind signal from the rain signal in the lidar data analysis process, to obtain a more precise wind speed measurement.

[11] proposed an iterative deconvolution method to separate the reflectivity spectrum of raindrops from the lidar power spectrum by using a vertically pointing coherent Doppler lidar, which is not applicable for horizontally pointing Doppler lidar. If lidars are already installed on the nacelle, it is worthwhile and potentially beneficial to use them to characterize the rain itself due to its role in leading edge erosion of wind turbine blades [12], so that the turbine can be

controlled based on the characteristics of the rain to reduce the erosion [13]. In this paper we limit ourselves to reducing the impact of rain on the wind signal while the characterization of rain with the lidar awaits further work.

Therefore, in this paper, by sampling the wind lidar rapidly up to 3000 Hz, we investigate the possibility of detecting and sieving out the rain spectra from the wind spectra.

2. Site and instrumentation

2.1. Site description

In order to validate the methodology for filtering away the rain signal, we conducted a field study at the Risø campus of Technical University of Denmark (DTU). We used a ground-based, continuous-wave (cw) Doppler lidar, which was installed in a van. The van was parked between a meteorological mast (met mast) and the DTU V52 wind turbine. The Doppler lidar was located 79.2 m away and 10° south of due east from the met mast, while the wind turbine is located 120.3 m away and 20° south of east from the same met mast, as shown in Figure 1.

The cw lidar measurements are compared with reference wind speeds that were measured at the met mast, before and after filtering away rain signals. There are five sonic anemometers and five cup anemometers, vertically placed at 18 m, 31 m, 44 m, 57 m, and 70 m heights. The sampling frequency of the sonic anemometers was 50 Hz. Risø cup anemometers were placed at the same heights but on booms opposing the sonic booms.

Figure 1. Top view of the experiment field at DTU Risø Campus. The DTU V52 wind turbine is located 120.3 m towards the southeast direction of the met mast and the cw lidar was found at 79.2 m southeast of the met mast (picture from Google Earth).

2.2. Doppler lidar

We use a mono-static, homodyne, infrared, coherent cw Doppler lidar, with an effective radius of the telescope equal to 18 mm, an elevation angle of 19.2° , an altitude about 9.22 m above the sea surface (1.9 m higher than the base of the met mast) and three focus distances about 20 m, 42.5 m, 85 m along the line-of-sight direction. In order to compare the wind speed measurements, we focus the lidar at the sonic anemometer located at 31 m height above ground level with a corresponding focus distance of 85 m along the line-of-sight direction where the probe length is about 22.2 m (defined here by twice the Rayleigh length z_R).

The analog to digital conversion of the photon detector signal is taking place at 120 MHz, and the cw lidar system employs the in-phase/quadrature-phase (IQ) detection method [14], which mixes the received signal with two local oscillator (LO) signals phase shifted by 90° relative to each other in order to be able to determine the sign of the line-of-sight velocity. A 1024-point Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) is applied to the acquired data, and the absolute

square of the DFT is computed to produce the spectra of the optical beat signal. Subsequently, the 40 spectra are averaged to produce the final Doppler spectra, which implies a sampling rate of 3000 Hz and a wind speed spectral resolution about 0.09 m/s.

Figure 2. *The mobile laboratory: the cw lidar was placed in a van. The laser beam was emitted through the open window that was facing the met mast.*

2.3. Measurement campaign

The measurement period is from 12:23 to 17:02 on October 5th, 2021. Due to the limitation of direct memory access (DMA) of the computer, sometimes the data acquisition was interrupted. The detailed information about the measurement setup is shown in Table 1. The rain intensity, the presence of raindrops in certain size intervals and their corresponding vertical velocities measured by the ground-based Ott Parsivel disdrometer are presented in Figure 3 [12]. The disdrometer is about 2 meters above the ground and located besides the met mast with its base 7.27 m above the sea surface.

We analysed the wind speed measured by the sonic anemometer at 31 m height when the lidar was focused at the same position. That was achieved when the lidar was focusing at 85 m along the slanted beam. There are three available periods, denoted a P1, P2 and P3 respectively, that are used for comparison. As shown in Figure 3, for these three periods, the intensity of the rain is about [1, 2.5] mm/h (indicated by the solid grey line) and the distribution of the raindrop sizes (the points) is almost the same for three periods. In this paper, we only show results for these three periods.

Table 1. *Measurement log on October 5th, 2021*

Line-of-sight focus distances	Time (UTC)	Total minutes
85 m	12:23-12:42 (P1)	20 minutes
	13:53-14:15 (P2)	22 minutes
	15:20-15:33 (P3)	13 minutes
42.5 m	13:01-13:22	22 minutes
	14:17-14:43	27 minutes
20 m	13:25-13:51	27 minutes
	14:45-15:17	33 minutes

Figure 3. Raindrop size, vertical speed (the points) of raindrops and the intensity of rain (the solid gray curve) on October 5th, 2021 from disdrometer measurement. The vertical gray bars represent the three periods when the lidar is focused 85 m away along the line-of-sight at the sonic anemometer at 31 m height above the ground. It rained continuously for three periods even though the intensity is not very high.

3. Sonic anemometer data

Before analysing the sonic and lidar data, we compare the wind speeds by the sonic and cup anemometers at all heights to verify the agreement of the sonic data. We find that the mean absolute deviation of 10-minute mean wind speeds at 31 m height is 0.08 m/s and that for wind direction between the sonic at 44 m and a wind vane at 41 m height is 1.73° , as shown in Figure 4. In Figure 4 (a), the mean wind speed at P1 is much smaller, about 2.5 m/s at 31 m height, compared with that at P2 and P3 which is around 4 m/s on average. For further comparison, we use the lidar's line-of-sight unit vector $[0.93, -0.17, -0.32]$ and project the wind vectors measured by sonic anemometer onto this.

Figure 4. Comparison of wind speed and direction measured by sonic and cup anemometers at five vertical heights (18, 31, 44, 57 and 70 m). The gray bars represent the three periods when the wind lidar was focused near the sonic anemometer at 31 m height. " W_{sp} " and " W_{dir} " are the wind speed and direction measured by the cup anemometer, while " SW_{sp} " and " S_{dir} " are those measured by the sonic anemometer. The horizontal, black line corresponds to the direction from the sonic anemometer to the center of the wind turbine.

During the period of the field study the wind direction changed as depicted in Figure 4

(b). At P1, the wind direction is about 123° from 12:23 to 12:42 (UTC+1), which is from the southeast. However, the wind direction changed to 87° in P2 and 75° in P3 (northeast). During the whole measurement period, the azimuth angle of the laser beam was 100° (or equivalently 280°) relative to the geographic North and the sonic anemometer was partly in the wake in P1 and P2, see figure Figure 4 (b).

4. Methodology to filter away rain signal

Large raindrops may fall with a velocity of up to 10 m/s in extreme cases and during the acquisition of one spectrum they fall at most 3.3 mm (but more typically for this data set around 1 mm) since the cw lidar produced 3000 laser Doppler spectra per second, which could potentially be used for further analysis to obtain the characteristic information of rain. Depending on how close the raindrop path is from the lidar focus and its fall velocity, a raindrop (see Figure 5 (a)) will give rise to one (at axial distance z'_1) or several spectra (at axial distance z'_2) with back-scatter from the drop.

The power spectral density (PSD) at a particular Doppler frequency corresponding to the raindrop's projected fall velocity is shown as a time series in Figure 5 (b) and it follows a Gaussian function of time (coincident with the findings from [15]) since the transverse intensity profile of the laser beam follows a Gaussian function. In this case, the drop seems to be away from the focus or it is falling slowly, so it takes several milliseconds for it to cross the beam.

Figure 5. The geometry of raindrops falling through a focused laser beam. (a) shows raindrops cross the laser beam at random positions, where $w(z)$ is the spot size along the beam, w_0 is the beam waist which is 2.35 mm in our case, z'_1 and z'_2 are two axial distances from the beam's focus, and z_R is the Rayleigh length which is 11.1 m. (b) presents the measurements of the power of the back-scattered signal at the Doppler frequency during a raindrop's passage through the beam, following a Gaussian distribution.

From Figure 3, we know that the vertical velocity ranges of raindrops for three periods are [0.25 m/s, 6.8 m/s] for P1, [0.3 m/s, 4.8 m/s] for P2, [0.3 m/s, 5.6 m/s] for P3. And the projections of these vertical velocities of raindrops on the lidar's line-of-sight direction for three periods are [0.08 m/s, 2.24 m/s], [0.99 m/s, 1.58 m/s], [0.99 m/s, 1.84 m/s], respectively. Depending on the size of raindrops, the location from the beam waist where the raindrops pass through the probe volume, as well as the position of raindrops at the cross-section of the laser beam, raindrop may generate a distinctive Doppler signal as shown in Figure 6 or negligible Doppler signal that can hardly be recognized.

We compare several consecutive spectra and found that the wind Doppler signal appears almost at the same position of the velocity bin and has a broader spectral width (as shown in Figure 6), while the rain Doppler signal has a very narrow peak. In Figure 6, the peak value of the rain Doppler signal is about two times larger than that of the wind signal. This could

be because the larger raindrop was passing the center axis of the laser beam and the back-scatters were strong since most of the laser beam energy is concentrated at the center axis. If the back-scatters by the rain are strong enough, they will dominate the total spectrum which one normally would use to determine the wind velocity, which may cause bias.

Figure 6. Examples of a normalized Doppler spectrum containing both wind and rain signal, after dividing by its own noise spectrum. The rightmost spike represents the Doppler shift by a raindrop. In our case, the line-of-sight velocity induced by rain is smaller than that by wind.

We first obtain the background noise spectrum of each single spectrum by calculating the median spectrum over 180,000 spectra from one-minute lidar data file, choosing the lower value between half of the median spectrum and the same half of the raw spectrum and mirroring to expand to a spectrum containing 1024 points. Then, the spectral threshold of each spectrum is estimated by averaging a flat range of the spectrum (50 points are included in our analysis). Finally, the raw spectra are normalized by dividing their own noise spectrum and subtracting with their own spectral threshold, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 7. Histograms of the maximum power spectral density values S_{max} of 180,000 raw spectra over a duration of one-minute lidar measurement for the three periods examined (P1, P2 and P3), respectively.

From the histogram of the maximum values of 180,000 raw spectra obtained during three one-minute periods (shown in Figure 7), we see that for P2 and P3, there are very strong rain signals (marked in the red circles) appearing at the rightmost part of the histograms, which will lead to the bias between the lidar data and the sonic data. However, for P1, there is no strong rain signal in the histogram and this is consistent with the results in Figure 9 (a) and (b).

Based on the above findings, we apply a broad range of threshold levels [1.25, 1.5, 2.0, 4.0, 10] to the normalized spectra to filter away rain signal. The method is that we discard spectra if their power spectral density values are greater than the threshold levels and keep only the spectra with lower peak energy (supposedly with no raindrops in the measurement volume) to derive wind velocity. For three periods, the absolute value of the difference between the one-second averaged line-of-sight wind speed by lidar and that by sonic, as a function of threshold levels is show in Figure 8.

For P1, applying thresholds to remove rain will enlarge the difference between the averaged wind speeds by lidar and that by sonic in that the strict thresholds, like 1.25, will remove 70% over 180,000 spectra of one-minute lidar data. However, for P2 and P3, when we choose the smallest threshold level 1.25, the difference between the filtered lidar and sonic wind speeds is the smallest. With the increasing of the threshold levels, the change of the difference of two instruments for these two periods increases and then tends to be the same for higher thresholds.

Figure 8. The absolute value of the difference of the averaged line-of-sight wind speeds by lidar and that by sonic, for three periods, as a function of threshold levels to filter away rain signal.

5. Results

In Figure 9, we compare the 1-second averaged raw lidar data (the red curve and dots), the filtered lidar data after applying threshold level 1.25 based on the results from Figure 8 (the blue curve and dots) with the sonic data (the cyan curve), respectively. For the comparison of P1, as shown in Figure 9 (a) and (b). The raw lidar data matches well with sonic data, which is consistent with the conclusions from Figure 7. From Figure 3 and Figure 4, we speculate that the reason that the lidar and sonic line-of-sight speeds compare well in P1 is that the resultant radial velocity of raindrops at this period is perpendicular to the lidar's line-of-sight. In this way, the projected component of the raindrops' speeds along the laser beam is zero.

When we apply very low threshold level 1.25 to the raw data of P1, the slope of the linear fit without an offset of the filtered results is 1.04 (the blue fitted line) and that of the raw lidar data is 0.96 (the red fitted line), as shown in Figure 9 (b). The parameters of the linear fit with an offset of the filtered lidar change only slightly compared to those of the raw data in P1. Besides, the coefficient of determination R^2 is slightly decreased from 0.739 to 0.706, which indicates that applying very strict threshold to filter away rain signal for P1 does not help significantly.

For P2 and P3, the results are promising as the difference between lidar data and sonic data is reduced and the slopes of the linear fits without offsets of the filtered lidar results are getting closer to one, changing from 0.85 to 0.94 in P2 and 0.71 to 0.87 in P3, as depicted in Figure 9 (c) to (f). The coefficient of determination R^2 of P2 is almost the same for the raw lidar data and the filtered, while for P3, it is slightly improved. Since we apply very low threshold level 1.25 to remove rain, the Doppler peaks induced by rain signal can be partly filtered away.

Figure 9. Comparison of the 1-second averaged raw lidar data (the red curve and dots), the filtered lidar data after applying threshold level 1.25 (the blue curve and dots) with sonic data at 31 m height (the cyan curve). The comparisons between the goodness-of-fit functions with (the dashed line) and without offsets (the solid line) of the raw lidar data (the red lines) and the filtered lidar data (the blue lines), as well as the coefficient of determination R^2 are shown in (b), (d), (f).

6. Conclusion

By sampling the Doppler spectra very rapidly up to 3000 Hz and applying different threshold levels, we can reduce the impact of the rain signal's impact on the wind speed determination. A more reliable measurement of the line-of-sight wind speed can thus be achieved during rain periods. The performance of different threshold levels to filter away rain signal depends on characteristics of the rain but how exactly, requires more experimentation to understand.

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